

Influence of Leadership Style and Employee Motivation toward Work Productivity of Employee Cooperation Operations PT. Angkasa Pura Solution with PT. Integreted Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS)

Susi Ernita Manurung, Togu Harlen Lbn. Raja, Amril

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi LMII, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Leadership style is an important aspect to achieve a successful leader where leadership style shows a strategy to influence subordinates so that the ups and downs of employee work productivity can be influenced by leadership style. Not only leadership style of employee work motivation also greatly affects employee work productivity because existing motivation in a person is a force that will drive to realize a behavior in order to achieve goals so that in this study, the authors use leadership style and employee work motivation as independent variables and work productivity employee as the dependent variable.

In this study, the authors used the associative method with a quantitative approach that is trying to describe the influence of the studied variables. The sampling technique in this study uses a simple random sampling, which is a random sampling technique without regard to strata in the population where the number of samples in this study were 64 respondents. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents who were employees of the Joint Operation of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi With PT. Integreted Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area. Data analysis used validity test, reliability test, classic assumption test, multiple linear regression analysis, t test, F test and R2 determination coefficient test operated through the SPSS 16 program.

The results of the t test on the leadership style variable obtained t_{count} of 3,940 > t_{table} of 1,670 this shows that part there is an influence of leadership style on employee work productivity that is equal to 45%. The results of the t test study of employee work motivation variables obtained t_{value} of 5.902 > t_{table} of 1.670 shows that part there is an influence of employee work motivation on employee work productivity that is equal to 60.3%. The results of the study in the F test obtained a calculated F_{value} of 71.112 > F_{table} of 3.15. This shows that the variables of leadership style and work motivation of employees together affect the work productivity of employees. The coefficient of determination, R^2 is 0.70 or 70%. So it can be concluded that the leadership style and work motivation of employees has an influence of 70% on employee work productivity.

KEYWORDS: Leadership Style, Motivation and Employee Work Productivity

1. Background.

The development of business competition in Indonesia greatly affects each company to provide the best by empowering existing resources in increasing employee productivity in the company. Increasing employee productivity is the duty of every company to be able to maintain the viability of the company by managing every resource effectively and efficiently.

Employee work productivity requires a creative person and employees are continuously encouraged to keep working and always innovating to come up with new ideas where it is a plan that must be realized by every company leader because increasing employee worker productivity is the end result expected by all companies. Productivity is not only

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seen from the concept of production and economics, but productivity is also seen from the concept of labor where human resources that are not considered important by management will have a negative impact on the company itself because employees who do not have the morale due to improper management will reduce employee productivity. It is important for every leader to continue to encourage his subordinates to work and achieve targets so that the company remains stable.

According to Whitmore in Dimas, 2017, states that employee work productivity is a measure of the use of resources in an organization which is usually expressed as the ratio of the total (Output) achieved with the resources used. Leaders

play an important role in managing every resource that is owned by every company where the ability of leaders and skills in directing is an important factor for achieving goals where a leader must be able to determine the strategies used in achieving these goals.

T. Hani Handoko, 1991, stated that leadership is defined as a process of directing and influencing the activities of a group of members who are interconnected with their duties. Leadership behavior will determine the development or failure of a company or organization through the leadership function (Leadership) and leadership style (Leadership Style) because leaders can influence morale and job satisfaction, security, quality of work life and the level of achievement of an organization or company. Leadership style is the way a leader moves his subordinates in which the success of the leader in moving his subordinates will have a good impact on employee productivity.

Employee work productivity relates to how the leadership is applied by a leader with the leadership style and motivation provided. Motivation is an activity that results in, channeling, and maintaining human behavior where the leader needs to understand the person's behavior and character before influencing or motivating him. Existing motivation in a person is a force that will drive to realize a behavior to achieve goals. Every employee who has a high work motivation will increase employee work productivity because the employee will have work spirit and will carry out their duties with satisfying results.

Given the importance of motivation, the company management needs to continue to motivate employees by paying attention to the motives or motivations that the employee wants. Motivation by every leader to every employee will encourage employees to work. The higher an employee's trust in their leaders and the high motivation of employees to work, the employee will increase work productivity.

PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) conduct operational cooperation with other companies aimed at creating quality and increasing company profits with proper management of the resources they have. According to direct observations of employees in the company are still found undisciplined and there are still many employees who do not come to work on the grounds of illness and absence. Granting leave, Back Up, Shift and EO privileges should not be found by employees who are not disciplined about attendance.

The decline in employee work discipline is a problem that will disrupt the operational system because the work that should be done by two people into one person will certainly reduce the quality because it is not affordable which will cause complaints from clients and it will also have an impact on employee productivity.

2. Problem Formulation.

The problems formulated to be discussed in this study are as follows:

- A. Is there an influence of Leadership Style on the Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

- B. Is there an influence of Employee Work Motivation on Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.
- C. Is there an influence of Employee Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

3. Research Objectives.

Based on the above problem formulation, the objectives of this research are as follows:

- A. To determine the effect of Leadership Style on Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.
- B. To determine the effect of Employee Work Motivation on Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.
- C. To determine the influence of Employee Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

4. Research Benefits.

A. For Authors.

It is hoped that this research can broaden and deepen insights and knowledge in the field of human resource management that the author has gained in lectures so far.

B. For Companies.

It is expected that the results of this study can help provide input for companies in developing leadership styles and are able to motivate each employee to work optimally.

C. For Other Parties.

This research is also expected to be a reference for researchers who will conduct research in the future.

5. Leadership Style.

Leadership style is the way a leader in moving each of his subordinates because an effective leadership style is a leader who is not only task-oriented, but how a leader must also have a good relationship with his subordinates. Leaders who tend to involve their subordinates in decision making and encourage each subordinate to continue to innovate in the achievement of company goals so that it will arouse the confidence and respect for subordinates to his superiors. A leader is the key to the ups and downs of work performance of his subordinates because employees who have enthusiasm for work will help leaders easily win.

Mulyono and Almas in Dimas, 2017, stated that there are three leadership styles, namely:

A. Autocratic Leadership Style.

A leader who considers the organization as private property identifies personal goals with organizational goals, considers subordinates as mere tools and does not want to accept criticism, suggestions and opinions, is too dependent on formal authority, and in action often uses an approach that contains an element of coercion.

B. Democratic Leadership Style.

A leader who is active, dynamic, directed, responsible, always willing to accept and respect the suggestions, opinions, and advice from subordinates, decision making is done by deliberation to reach an agreement, and treat subordinates more humanely.

C. Free Full Leadership Style (Laissez-Faire).

A leader who shows passive behavior often avoids responsibility and tends to let the organization run according to its own tempo, where its position as a leader is only a symbol and decision-making made by each member, so it can be said that subordinates are given full freedom in making decisions.

6. Employee Motivation.

Every human being needs encouragement to build themselves to do the best where encouragement or motivation is very important so that individuals have goals and act to fulfill their needs were in a company or organization employees must be encouraged to work and try to achieve it to the maximum in order to achieve company goals. Motivation is a mobilizer from one's heart to act where the process of achieving that goal really requires a strong determination to encourage the person to remain enthusiastic in working so that the goal can be achieved.

In a company, organization or daily life everyone has a fear of something, but someone who has hope and continues to think positively will encourage them to continue to do and try to achieve success where in the company or organization's one's motives for achieving success are also very influential because when the person wants status or recognition, then he will try as much as possible to do the good of others. Motivating employees is not new for every company because it is recognized as being able to encourage them to work with enthusiasm. Encouragement or motivation is not only obtained from the company, but the family also plays a role in giving encouragement so that it arouses passion in the person in working by instilling in his heart that his family is a priority for him. Motivation to talk is not just an external impulse, but motivation from within oneself is something that really needs to be built by everyone because not many people are able to be a motivator for others and even succeed in motivating that person, but when self-motivating with expectations strong by not complaining about existing problems, then he will try with confidence and continue to look for a way out and achieve success.

Mangkunegara, 2017, stated that work motivation is formed from the attitudes of employees in dealing with work situations in the company.

Fillmore H. Stanford in Mangkunegara, 2017, stated that motivation is a condition that moves people towards a certain goal. Motivation is also interpreted as energy to generate impulses within.

Abraham Maslow, 1994, stated that motivation is a strength (energy) of a person which can cause a level of persistence and enthusiasm in carrying out an activity both originating from within the individual and from outside the individual itself.

7. Employee Work Productivity.

Increased Productivity is something that every company or organization wants to achieve where an increase in productivity will make the company survive from its competitors. Productivity is not just talking about profit, but increasing worker productivity of each employee is also very much needed where every human resource is required to be able to provide the best for the company where he works. Employee work productivity requires a mental attitude that wants to think ahead and develop themselves to remain consistent with predetermined goals. Achieving good work productivity can be achieved by anyone, but maintaining work productivity remains consistent, even beyond expectations is a task that must be realized by every manager of the company.

Sutrisno, 2016, states that productivity is generally defined as the relationship between output (goods or services) and inputs (labor, materials, money). Productivity is also defined as productive efficiency, which is a comparison between output and input.

Tohardi in Sutrisno, 2016, stated that work productivity is a mental attitude that is always looking for improvements to what already exists. A belief that someone can do a better job today than yesterday and tomorrow is better than today. Human resources are an element that plays a very important role in every company and also an organization where the increase in work productivity is only possible by humans if managed properly.

Then M. N. Nasution in Salis, 2017, states that productivity is the ratio between the results of activities (outputs) and all the sacrifices (inputs) in producing something. Productivity means the comparison between the results achieved with the overall resources used.

8. Previous Research.

Previous research is a measure and a picture of the writer to see and compare the results of previous studies concerning leadership style, employee work motivation and employee work productivity so that it can help the writer to develop a framework for thinking in this study. Previous research in this study helps us to build hypotheses on the basis that this research has been done by someone else. The previous research which is almost related to the leadership style and work motivation of employees to employee work productivity is as follows:

- A. Husna, 2012, states that the influence of leadership style on work productivity has a positive effect, this is evidenced from the Chi-Square results of 19.715 greater than the Chi-square table with a 95% confidence level.
- B. Istiqomah and Heru, 2018, stated that leadership style affects employee performance by 40.4% and 59.6% is influenced by other factors.
- C. Dimas, 2017, stated that the leadership style and motivation for work productivity at BRI Bank in Tanjung Pinang were 0.183, which had an effect of 18.3%.
- D. Martin, 2017, states that the leadership style on employee work productivity has a significant effect both simultaneously and partially by 0.675 or 67.5% and by 0.325 or 32.5% influenced by other factors.
- E. Bryan, 2014, stated that leadership style has a positive influence on employee performance. This can be seen from the tcount of 2.098 with a significance level of

0.043 that is smaller than 0.5, while motivation also has a positive influence on employee performance with a tcount of 3.909 with a significance level of results of 0.000 is less than 0.05.

- F. Salis, 2017, states that motivation has a positive influence on employee work productivity. It is proven that motivation affects the work of employees by 86.86% and 13.14% is influenced by other factors.
- G. Desi Rahmawati, 2013, stated that motivation affects employee work productivity by 34.2%, which includes salaries, bonuses and promotions.

9. Thinking Framework.

In a research framework of thinking is made to facilitate the flow of thought that has been set by researchers where the framework of thinking will describe the existing problems with the support of theories that explain these variations. The framework of thinking is made by the researcher to conceptually describe the problem formulation that exists in this study because before forming the research paradigm, the researcher must develop a framework of thinking with the support of theories about the variables that have been determined in the study (Figure 2.1).

According to Uma Sekaran in Melva Sitanggang and Togu Harlen Lumban Raja, 2011, explained that the framework of thinking is conceptual about how theories relate to various factors that have been identified as important problems.

Information:

- X1 : Leadership Style.
- X2 : Employee Work Motivation.
- Y : Employee Work Productivity.

10. Premise.

The premise is the basis of conclusions or rationale where researchers make the premise as a basis for supporting hypotheses. The premise is obtained from previous studies that illustrate that leadership style variables and employee work motivation have an influence on employee work productivity. In this case it can be interpreted that the premise is drawing conclusions about the variables studied.

Melva Sitanggang and Togu Harlen Lumban Raja, 2011, stated that the premise is the basis of logic or the basis of thought that forms a process of reasoning based on logic that seeks to connect two different propositions to draw conclusions. In this study, the authors make the premise that the conclusions drawn from previous research as a guide for the authors to support this research.

Premise 1

Husna, 2012, stated that the Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Work Productivity of the Workshop Section on CV Mitra Denso Bandar Lampung has a positive influence on employee work productivity. This is evidenced by the results of the Chi-Square calculation of 19.715 greater than the Chi-square table with a 95% confidence level.

Premise 2

Istiqomah and Heru, 2018, stated that the Effect of Leadership Style on Performance with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable (Study of Employees at Kebon Agung Malang Factory) has an influence on employee performance by 40.4% and 59.6% influenced by other factors.

Premise 3

Dimas, 2017, stated that the Leadership Style and Motivation of Employee Work Productivity at Tanjung Pinang BRI Bank had an influence on employee work productivity of 18.3%.

Premise 4

Martin, 2017, stated that the Leadership Style Towards Employee Productivity at PT. Malang Coca-Cola branch has a significant influence on employee work productivity both simultaneously and also partially as much as 0.675 or 67.5% and as much as 0.325 or 32.5% influenced by other factors.

Premise 5

Bryan, 2014, stated that the Leadership Style and Motivation Toward Employee Performance at PT. Bank Negara Indonesia, Tbk has a positive influence on employee performance. This can be seen from the count of 2.098 with a significance level of 0.043 that is smaller than 0.5, while motivation also has a positive influence on employee performance with a count of 3.909 with a significance level of results of 0.000 is less than 0.05.

Premise 6

Salish, 2017, stated that the Motivation of Employee Work Productivity at PT. Arka Mahesa Pratama in South Jakarta stated that motivation has a positive influence on employee work productivity. It is proven that motivation affects the work of employees by 86.86% and 13.14% is influenced by other factors.

Premise 7

Desi Rahmawati, 2013, entitled The Effect of Motivation on Employee Work Productivity of PR Fajar Berlin Tulungagung stated that the motivation has an influence on employee work productivity by 34.2%, which includes Salary, Bonus and Promotion.

11. Hypothesis.

Hypothesis is a statement made in a study and must be proven true where the basis for the formation of a hypothesis is taken from the premise of the conclusion drawn from previous research. The existence of a hypothesis will form several statements whose truth must be proven through data and analyzed with statistical test equipment.

Proof of the truth will help researchers see whether there is an influence of each independent variable affecting the dependent variable either partially or simultaneously. Proof of truth must be supported by data and theories that support each of the variables so that it will be easier for researchers to prove supported by the statistical test equipment.

According to Sudjana in Melva Sitanggang and Togu Harlen Lumban Raja, 2011, states that the hypothesis is an assumption or conjecture about something that is made to explain it that is often required to carry out checks.

Then Sugiyono, 2013, explained that the hypothesis is a temporary answer to the formulation of the research problem where the research problem formulation has been

stated in the form of sentence questions. It was said temporarily because the answers were only given based on relevant theories and were not based on empirical facts obtained through data collection so that hypotheses could also be expressed as theoretical answers to the formulation of research problems not yet empirical answers. From the description above, the hypotheses of this research area:

- A. Leadership Style has an influence on the Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.
- B. Employee Work Motivation has an influence on the Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.
- C. Leadership Style and Work Motivation Employees have an influence on the Employee Productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

12. Research Methods.

The research method is a scientific method used by researchers to obtain data for specific purposes where the method used in this study is an associative method with a quantitative approach that seeks to describe the effect of the variable under study.

Sugiyono, 2013, stated that associative research is research that aims to find out the influence or relationship between two or more variables.

The independent variables in this study are the leadership style (X1) and employee work motivation (X2) and the dependent variable namely employee work productivity (Y). With this associative method, it can be seen the influence of leadership style and employee work motivation on the employee work productivity of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

13. Research Place and Time.

In accordance with the title of this study, the location of the study is PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area. The research period is four months, starting from May to September 2019.

14. Population.

Population is the overall object of research that functions as a source of data that will be explained as a research object where the population can also be interpreted as the totality of all values used to calculate and measure the variables studied. The goal is to have a population so that researchers can determine the size of the sample to be determined in the study.

Population in statistics is a group of individuals that are of concern in research where in a study both thesis, thesis, and dissertation the existence of a population has an important role because the population will determine the number of samples that will be used as data sources in research.

According to Syofian Siregar, 2015, the population is the whole (Universum) of the object of research which can be humans, animals, plants, air, symptoms, values, events, attitudes to life and so on so that they serve as research objects.

Sugiyono, 2013, stated that the population is a generalized area consisting of objects / subjects, which have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The population in this study was all employees of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

15. Samples.

Samples are part of the population where a good sample must meet the requirements to ensure population stability. Sampling is a process of selecting and determining the type of sample and calculating the size of the sample that will be the subject or object of research. The sampling technique in this study uses simple random sampling, which is a random sampling technique without regard to strata in the population. In a sampling study conducted must be able to describe the characteristics of the population, the data obtained is accurate data.

Sugiyono, 2013, stated that the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. To calculate the sample used in this study is the sloven formula. According to Syofian Siregar, the 2015 sample count is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

$$n = \frac{175}{1 + (175 \times (0,1)^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{175}{1 + (175 \times 0,01)}$$

$$n = \frac{175}{1 + 1,75}$$

$$n = \frac{175}{2,75}$$

$$n = 63,63$$

$$n = 64$$

Information:

n : Number of samples.

N : Total population.

e : Percent of allowance for sampling that can be tolerated (e in this study is determined at 10%).

so the number of samples in this study were 64 people.

16. Data collection technique.

Data collection techniques are ways that are used to obtain data and information needed in research. Data collection techniques correctly will help researchers obtain accurate data where the data obtained will be processed and become a source of information so that you will see an explanation of each variable to be examined.

Data collection techniques need to be done in the right way because wrong data will affect the final results of a study. Data collection can also be obtained from various sources so that more data is obtained, so the more information obtained by researchers to assist in their research. Data collection techniques used in this study are as follows:

A. Primary data.

Data obtained directly from respondents using a questionnaire on the employees of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

B. Secondary data.

Data obtained from the company PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.

17. Instrument Validity Test.

Validity testing is testing conducted to find out whether the tools used in measuring instruments can be used in measuring. Validity indicates the extent to which a measuring device may be used by researchers in research.

Sugiyono, 2013, valid means that the instrument can be used to measure what should be measured. In this study, if the correlation is above 0.3, it is said that the item provides a sufficient degree of validity, otherwise if the value of the correlation is below 0.3, it is said that the item is less valid. After that, if coun t> table means that the data is significant and feasible to be used in testing the research hypothesis. Conversely, if a count table means that the data is not significant and is not used in testing the research hypothesis.

Surfing Siregar, 2015, stated in finding the correlation coefficient value using the following formula:

$$r = \frac{n \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{n[\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Information:

- r = correlation coefficient.
- $\sum XY$ = Number of multiplications between variables X and Y.
- $\sum X^2$ = Number of squares of X values.
- $\sum Y^2$ = Number of squares of value Y.
- $\sum(X)^2$ = Number of X values squared.
- $\sum(Y)^2$ = Number of Y values squared.
- n = Number of respondents.

After the correlation number is known, the t value of r is calculated using the formula:

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{(n-2)}}{\sqrt{(1-r^2)}}$$

After that compared with the critical value if count > table means that the data is significant (valid) and feasible to be used in testing the research hypothesis. Conversely, if a count table means that the data is not significant (invalid) and will not be included in testing the research hypothesis. The valid statements are then tested for reliability.

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	137.50	301.167	.930	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.90	291.656	.924	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.90	291.656	.924	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	137.30	303.122	.818	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.10	316.322	.107	.986
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.90	291.656	.924	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.90	286.544	.961	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Gaya Kepemimpinan	136.40	301.600	.886	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.80	294.844	.896	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.80	294.844	.896	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.70	292.233	.936	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	137.30	303.122	.818	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.90	291.656	.924	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.40	301.600	.886	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.30	303.122	.818	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	137.30	303.122	.818	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	137.20	298.178	.835	.984
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	137.20	308.400	.390	.986
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.30	310.456	.405	.985
Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	136.60	292.711	.877	.984
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	136.70	292.233	.936	.984
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	136.50	301.167	.930	.984
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	136.80	294.844	.896	.984
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	137.00	296.000	.849	.984
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	137.20	310.622	.295	.986
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	136.40	305.600	.663	.985
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	136.70	299.567	.828	.984
Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan	136.70	308.233	.654	.985

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Item-Total Statistics tested each statement item so that it appears that there are statement items under 0.3 where the statement item is contained in statement number 9 on the leadership style variable and statement number 31 in the employee productivity variable so it can be concluded that the statement is not valid and will not be used in the next test.

18. Instrument Reliability Test.

Reliability test is a determination in measuring where whenever the instrument used to measure will give the same results because the instrument reliability test is used to find out whether the data collection tool shows the level of accuracy, level of stability, stability, or consistency in expressing certain symptoms (Sugiyono, 2013). To test the reliability of the author using the Cronbach Alpha method, namely to calculate the reliability of a test that does not have a choice of right or wrong or yes or no, but to calculate the reliability of a test that measures attitudes or behavior. If the correlation is 0.6 or more, the item is said to provide a reliable level. which is sufficient, on the contrary, if the correlation value is below 0.6 then it is said that the item is less reliable.

Syofian Siregar, 2015, Reliability measurement techniques used in this study with the following formula:

$$r = \frac{k}{k-1} \left[1 - \frac{\sum \sigma^2 b}{\sigma^2 t} \right]$$

Information:

- n = Number of samples.
- X_i = Respondents' answers to each question.
- ∑X = Total respondent's answer for each question.
- σ² t = Variant Total.
- ∑σ² b = Number of Item Variants.

- k = Number of Question Points.
- r₁₁ = instrument reliability coefficient.

after getting the instrument reliability, value (rcount), the value is compared with r table. If recent > table, the instrument is said to be reliable, conversely, if recent table, the instrument is said to be not reliable.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.987	32

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Reliability Statistics it can be seen that the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.987 so it can be interpreted that the statement or measuring instrument to be used in this study is reliable because it is greater than the predetermined criteria which is equal to 0.6.

19. Classical Assumption Test Results.

19.1. Normality test.

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on the Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residuals it can be seen that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line indicating that the distribution pattern is normal so that the normality test is met.

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

19.2. Multicollinearity Test.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	5.962	2.136		2.791	.007		
	Gaya Kepemimpinan	.177	.045	.366	3.940	.000	.569	1.758
	Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	.270	.046	.549	5.902	.000	.569	1.758

Based on the results of SPSS 16 output on Coefficients it can be seen that the coefficient of VIF <10 so that it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity and it can be concluded that the data used escapes classical assumptions because there is no multicollinearity.

19.3. Heteroscedasticity Test.

Scatterplot

Based on the results of SPSS 16 output on the Scatterplot image, it can be seen that the distribution of points in the plot does not indicate the existence of a certain pattern, so it can be said that the model is free from the assumption of heteroscedasticity.

19.4. Multiple Linear Regression Results.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	5.962	2.136		2.791	.007		
	Gaya Kepemimpinan	.177	.045		3.940	.000	.569	1.758
	Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	.270	.046		5.902	.000	.569	1.758

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Coefficients describe the regression equation as follows :
 $Y = 5.962 + 0.177 X_1 + 0.270 X_2$

Where :

- a : The constant number of Unstandardized Coefficients is 5,962.
- B₁ : The first regression coefficient number at X₁ (Leadership Style) is 0.177.
- B₂ : The second regression coefficient number at X₂ (Employee Work Motivation) is 0.270.

20. Hypothesis Results.

20.1. The Effect of Leadership Style (X1) on Employee Productivity (Y).

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	
1	(Constant)	5.962	2.136		2.791	.007			
	Gaya Kepemimpinan	.177	.045		3.940	.000	.727	.450	.276
	Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	.270	.046		5.902	.000	.790	.603	.414

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output in the Coefficients table for the first regression coefficient the leadership style variable significantly shows that the results of the count of 3,940 > t table of 1,670 so that H_a is accepted and H₀ is rejected and it can be concluded that the leadership style partially affects employee productivity partially that is equal to 0.450 or that the work productivity of employees at PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi with PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) is influenced by the leadership style of 45%.

20.2. Effect of Employee Work Motivation (X2) On Employee Work Productivity (Y).

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	
1	(Constant)	5.962	2.136		2.791	.007			
	Gaya Kepemimpinan	.177	.045		3.940	.000	.727	.450	.276
	Motivasi Kerja Karyawan	.270	.046		5.902	.000	.790	.603	.414

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on Coefficients for the second regression coefficient of employee work motivation variables show the results of t value of 5.902 > t table of 1.670 so that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted and it can be concluded that the partially employee motivation has a significant influence on work productivity employees amounted to 0.603 or that employee work motivation affects employee productivity by 60.3%.

20.3. The Effect of Leadership Style (X1) and Employee Motivation (X2) on Employee Productivity (Y).

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	182.472	2	91.236	71.112	.000 ^a
	Residual	78.263	61	1.283		
	Total	260.734	63			

Based on the output of the SPSS 16 program output on Anova rebel, the calculated F value is 71.112 > F table is 3.15, which means that H_a is rejected and H₀ is accepted. So it can be concluded that the leadership style and work motivation of employees jointly influence the variable work productivity of employees.

20.4. Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.837 ^a	.700	.690	1.133

Based on the output of the SPSS 16 program output in the Model Summary table, the R Square value is 0.70 or 70%. So it can be concluded that the leadership style and work motivation of employees has an influence of 70% on employee work productivity and 30% is influenced by others factors not examined in this study.

21. Conclusion.

Based on the results of research in which the purpose of this study is to find out "The Effect of Leadership Style and Employee Work Motivation on Employee Productivity in the Operational Cooperation of PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi and PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch Kualanamu Airport area "were based on research and data processing results that have been carried out in this study the following conclusions are obtained:

- A. Based on the results of the hypothesis on the results of the T test of the leadership style variables obtained a count value of $3.940 > t$ table of 1.670 so that it can be concluded that part there is an influence between the leadership style variables on employee work productivity variables.
- B. Based on the results of the hypothesis on the results of the T test on the variable of employee motivation obtained count value of $5.902 > t$ table of 1.670 so that it can be concluded that part there is an influence between the variable of employee motivation on employee work productivity variables.
- C. Based on the results of the hypothesis on the results of the F Test obtained the calculated F value of $71.112 > F$ table of 3.15 so that it can be concluded that the variations of leadership style and employee work motivation together affect the employee work productivity variables.
- D. Based on the results of the Determination Coefficient Test (R²) the R Square value of 0.70 is obtained. This means that the variables of leadership style and employee work motivation influence the variable work productivity of employees by 70% on employee work productivity and 30% are influenced by other factors, not examined in this study such as the work environment, other organizational culture and so on.

22. Suggestions.

After conducting research, discussion, and drawing conclusions from the results of the research, the authors provide suggestions relating to the research that has been done to be used as input and material considerations that are useful for interested parties, namely as follows:

- A. For Joint Operation Companies PT. Angkasa Pura Solusi and PT. Integrated Service Solutions (KSO APS-ISS) Medan Branch in Kualanamu Airport area.
Seeing the magnitude of the influence between leadership style and employee work motivation on employee work productivity, it is very important for leaders to continue to improve the quality of leadership and continue to motivate and encourage each employee so that they can provide better results to the responsibilities that have been given to them .
- B. For Further Researchers.
The next researcher is expected to be able to analyze other variables are factors that increase employee productivity, such as the work environment, organizational culture and so on.

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